

Enhancing the Enzymatic Digestibility of Sugarcane Bagasse through the Application of an Ionic Liquid in Combination with an Acid Catalyst

Danie Diedericks¹, Eugéne van Rensburg¹, María del Prado García-Aparicio¹, and Johann F. Görgens¹

¹*Department of Process Engineering, Stellenbosch University, Private Bag XI
Stellenbosch 7602 South Africa*

* Corresponding author: Email: jgorgens@sun.ac.za

Citation

Diedericks, D.; van Rensburg, E.; García-Aparicio, M. del P.; Görgens, J.F. *Enhancing the enzymatic digestibility of sugarcane bagasse through the application of an ionic liquid in combination with an acid catalyst*. *Biotechnology Progress*, 28(1), 2012, 76–84. DOI: 10.1002/btpr.711

Access conditions

Due to copyright restrictions and the age of the publication, only metadata have been deposited in a public repository. The published version is available from the journal *Biotechnology Progress* via the DOI provided above.

Enhancing the Enzymatic Digestibility of Sugarcane Bagasse through the Application of an Ionic Liquid in Combination with an Acid Catalyst

Danie Diedericks¹, Eugène van Rensburg¹, María del Prado García-Aparicio¹, and Johann F. Görgens*¹

¹*Department of Process Engineering, Stellenbosch University, Private Bag XI Stellenbosch 7602 South Africa*

* *Corresponding author: Email: jgorgens@sun.ac.za*

Abstract

Various ionic liquids have been identified as effective pretreatment solvents that can enhance the cellulose digestibility of lignocellulose by removing lignin, one of the main factors contributing to the recalcitrant nature of lignocellulose. 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium methylsulfate ([BMiM]MeSO₄) is a potential delignification reagent, hence its application as a pretreatment solvent for sugarcane bagasse (SB) was investigated. The study also evaluated the benefit of an acid catalyst (i.e., H₂SO₄) and the effect of pretreatment conditions, which varied within a time and temperature range of 0-240 min and 50-150°C, respectively. The use of an acid catalyst contributed to a more digestible solid and a higher degree of delignification. However, the [BMiM]MeSO₄-H₂SO₄ combination failed to produce a fully digestible solid, as a maximum cellulose digestibility of 77% (w/w) was obtained at the optimum pretreatment condition of 125°C for 120 min. Furthermore, up to half of the lignin content could be extracted during pretreatment, while simultaneously extensive, sometimes complete, removal of xylan, the presence of which, also hampers cellulose digestibility. Hence, [BMiM]MeSO₄ has been identified an effective pretreatment solvent for SB as the application thereof both significantly improved digestibility, and simultaneously removed two of the main factors contributing to the recalcitrant nature of lignocellulose. As xylan and lignin have potential value as precursor chemicals, the existing process may in future be extended toward substrate fractionation, a biorefinery concept where value is added to all feedstock constituents.

Keywords: ionic liquid, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium methylsulfate, delignification, cellulose digestibility, sugarcane bagasse